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Celle Plumage and Integument Condition Scoring System for Welfare and Health in Laying Hens

based on LayWel*

*www.laywel.eu

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Neck, back, breast, belly, tail, wings (cover feathers and wing feathers)

Scores 4, 3, 2, 1

Score 4 = intact plumage with no or only mild wear, i.e. damaged or deformed feathers
wings: ≤ 5 damaged* feathers

Score 3 = skin still completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area $< 5 \text{ cm}^2$ (approx. $< 2.2 \times 2.3 \text{ cm}$)
wings: approx. 6 - 10 damaged* feathers

Score 2 = severely damaged feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area $\geq 5 \text{ cm}^2$
wings: approx. 11 - 15 damaged* feathers

Score 1 = very severe plumage damage with no or only few feathered areas
featherless area $> 5 \text{ cm}^2$ AND predominantly featherless or completely featherless
wings: approx. ≥ 16 damaged* feathers or almost completely featherless

*Definition of "damaged": broken feathers or at least 1 cm featherless spots on both sides of the quill.

Scores wings: The wing with the more severe damage is used for the evaluation. The assessment is either made on the basis of the cover feathers or wing feathers depending on which are most severely damaged.

Head

Scores 0, 1

Score 0 = completely feathered

Score 1 = damaged feathers, featherless areas or completely featherless

Plumage Condition

Neck

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers

Score 3

skin still completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area $< 5 \text{ cm}^2$ (approx. $< 2.2 \times 2.3 \text{ cm}$)

Score 2

severely damaged feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area $\geq 5 \text{ cm}^2$

Score 1

very severe plumage damages with no or only few feathered areas
featherless area $> 5 \text{ cm}^2$ AND predominantly featherless or completely featherless

Plumage Condition

Back

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers

Score 3

skin still completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area $< 5 \text{ cm}^2$ (approx. $< 2.2 \times 2.3 \text{ cm}$)

Score 2

severely damaged feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area $\geq 5 \text{ cm}^2$

Score 1

very severe plumage damage with no or only few feathered areas
featherless area $> 5 \text{ cm}^2$ AND predominantly featherless or completely featherless

Plumage Condition

Wing

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers
wings: ≤ 5 damaged* feathers

Score 3

skin still completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area $< 5 \text{ cm}^2$ (approx. $< 2.2 \text{ cm} \times 2.3 \text{ cm}$)
wings: approx. 6 - 10 damaged* feathers

Score 2

severely damaged feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area $\geq 5 \text{ cm}^2$.
wings: approx. 11 - 15 damaged* feathers

Score 1

very severe plumage damage with no or only a few feathered areas
featherless area $> 5 \text{ cm}^2$ AND predominantly or completely featherless
wings: approx. ≥ 16 damaged* feathers or almost completely featherless

*Definition of "damaged": broken feathers or at least 1 cm bare spots on both sides of the quill.

Plumage Condition

Tail

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers, ≤ 5 feathers damaged

Score 3

6 - 8 damaged* feathers

Score 2

9 - 12 severely damaged* feathers

Score 1

≥ 13 severely damaged* feathers or almost completely featherless

* Definition of "damaged": broken feathers or at least 1 cm bare spots on both sides of the quill.

Plumage Condition

Breast

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers

Score 3

skin completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area < 5 cm² (approx. < 2.2 x 2.3 cm)

Score 2

severely damaged* feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area ≥ 5 cm²

Score 1

very severe plumage damage with no or only few feathered areas
featherless area > 5 cm² AND predominantly or completely featherless

Plumage Condition

Belly

Score 4

intact plumage with no or only a few damaged or deformed feathers

Score 3

skin still completely or almost completely covered with feathers
featherless area $< 5 \text{ cm}^2$ (approx. $< 2.2 \times 2.3 \text{ cm}$)

Score 2

severely damaged feathers and/or featherless areas
featherless area $\geq 5 \text{ cm}^2$

Score 1

very severe plumage damage with no or only few feathered areas
featherless area $> 5 \text{ cm}^2$ AND predominantly or completely featherless

Keelbone damage

Inspection and palpation on living* animals.

Scores 4, 3, 2

Score 4 = without any particular findings

Score 3 = minor deviations palpable (slightly S-shaped and/or dorsoventral compression and/or slight irregularities in the structure)

Score 2 = strong deviations in shape and/or structure, palpable bone formations (indication of fracture)

* For better documentation, pictures were taken after the skin had been removed.

Cannibalism / Injury / Comb (Pecks)

Cannibalism:

Scores 0, 1

- Score 0 = not present
- Score 1 = present, bloody injury

Injuries:

Scores 0, 1

- Score 0 = not present
- Score 1 = present

Pecks:

The pecks are counted from both sides of the comb and summed up.

Foot pad / digital pads

Hyperkeratosis

Hyperkeratosis:

Independent scoring of foot pad and digital pads on both feet

Scores 0, 1

Score 0 = no or minor hyperkeratosis

Score 1 = medium to severe hyperkeratosis

Score 0

(foot pad and digital pads)

Score 1

(digital pads)

Score 1

(foot pad)

Score 1

(foot pad)

Foot pad / digital pads

Epithelial lesions

Epithelial lesions:

Independent scoring of foot pad and digital pads at both feet

Scores 4, 3, 2, 1

- Score 4 = no lesions
- Score 3 = minor, superficial lesion, max. 2 mm, no swelling
- Score 2 = lesion but no swelling visible from dorsal side, ≥ 2 mm, possibly thickened
- Score 1 = severe lesion, swelling visible from dorsal side (acutely inflamed)

Foot pad / digital pads

Epithelial lesions

minor, superficial lesion, max. 2 mm, no swelling

Score 3
(foot pad)

score 1
(digital pads)

severe lesion, swelling visible from the dorsal side (acutely inflamed)

Score 1
(digital pad)

severe lesion, swelling visible from the dorsal side (acutely inflamed)

Claw length / claws broken off

Claw length:

For claw length, the right, middle toe is measured along the dorsal surface with a flexible measuring tape.

Claws broken off:

All toes are checked for broken claws.

Scores 0, 1

Score 0 = no (no broken claw)

Score 1 = yes (≥ 1 broken claws)

